

TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES TO STUDENTS WITH DIFFERENT LEVELS OF PROFICIENCY

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Buxoro viloyat ftiziatriya sihatgohi Maktabi ingliz tili fani o'qituvchisi

Abstract: *Despite the fact that the initial level of lexical and grammatical knowledge and listening of a group can vary greatly, all students is supposed to acquire equal levels of a full-fledged foreign-language communicative competence. To achieve this, a teacher needs to differentiate and individualize both the contents and approaches to teaching. It is considered possible ways of differentiating and individualizing the learning process. The ways of individualization of the contents of foreign language teaching are analyzed. The paper proposes the tasks that range from reproductive to productive level, which allow differentiating the learning process. It recommends methods for assessing students depending on their initial level of foreign language skills. The article also gives practical recommendations on the application of group learning technologies and examines how this impacts positively on the mastering of foreign language communicative competence by students in non-linguistic higher education institutions.*

Keywords: *multilevel group, personality-oriented teaching methods, foreign language communicative competence, non-linguistic higher education institution, group learning technologies.*

INTRODUCTION

Teaching any foreign language in a non-linguistic university is carried out in conditions of heterogeneity of study groups made up of students who initially have different levels of language training and different abilities to learn the language. In these conditions, students' mastering of foreign language communicative competence is difficult. The purpose of this work is to find ways to solve the problem of teaching in one group of students with different levels of language training.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

One of the possible ways out of this situation is the organization of personality-oriented differentiated training, which "in relation to the process of teaching a foreign language to students of non-linguistic universities is understood as such a system of training, which takes into account the individual psychological characteristics of each student and in which each student is provided with a real opportunity to act as a subject of training" [1]. Differentiation in the process of teaching a foreign language is traditionally considered from three different positions [2]:

1. Differentiation of the training content.

The content includes the knowledge, skills, and abilities that the student must master as a result of training. Of course, at the end of the course, all students must pass tests and exams according to a single program, i.e. reach a certain mandatory level for all. However, the number of unknown, i.e. subject to study units of educational material may be different for each student.

Differentiation of the learning process

It means that the teacher allows each student to choose different ways of mastering the content. The language abilities of students are manifested not only in the speed, ease and strength of mastering the educational material, but also in the preferred and most successfully implemented forms of educational activity. Students can complete various tasks depending on their level of training, needs, and interests.

Differentiation of learning outcomes

It means the variety of levels of complexity of cognitive products that students create to show mastery in mastering the content of learning. The need to differentiate the content of training requires a preliminary determination of the language level of students. This can be done by using input diagnostic testing. This information allows the teacher to plan the learning process. The problem of the level of language proficiency became particularly relevant in the second half of the XX century in connection with the expansion of international cooperation and the formation of the concept of "Europe without Borders", in which much attention was paid to the study of foreign languages. "The level of language proficiency is understood as the degree of formation of speech skills and abilities of the user in the studied language" [3, p. 56]. By the decision of the Council of Europe, the document "Common European Framework of Reference: Learning, Teaching, Assessment" was developed. Competencies are based on a single principle of assessment and training. "Currently, within the framework of university education, it is not customary to record the results of the exam in terms of the European level classification: level A1, A2, etc. However, it should be borne in mind that if there is a need for international conversion of estimates, there is every reason to draw certain parallels and correspondences between the test results in different evaluation systems" [4, p.17]. In the event that the input diagnostic testing reveals a different initial language level of students in one group, it is necessary to differentiate the content and, as a result, the entire learning process in such a group. The content is differentiated with the help of multi-level tasks that allow all students to be involved in the course of the lesson. Students are given tasks within one of three possible levels:

- 1.reproductive
2. reproductive-productive,
- 3.productive (creative).

For example, students with a low level of proficiency in a foreign language are given reproductive tasks, such as retelling a pre-parsed text. When working with such students, you can use the "improve and repeat" method, which is used in groups or frontally [5, p. 337]. This method helps slow learners to understand and memorize new

material. The work is structured as follows: after the teacher introduces the information, students help one of the members of their group to prepare for a speech to their group. The speaker's task is to repeat the teacher's words as accurately as possible. When reading, you can use the Rivin method of paragraph-by-paragraph study of the text [6, p. 312]. The work is carried out with different paragraphs of the same text or with different microtexts in replaceable pairs, in which students together find the main idea and key words of the paragraph(microtext), make a heading, and then, using the written out keywords, convey the content of the paragraphs. The average level of language proficiency allows you to combine what you have previously learned with elements of independent utterance. Students of a high level of language proficiency willingly perform tasks that require complete independence, prefer productive, creative work. Intermediate and high-level students are encouraged to offer open-ended assignments that allow each student to maximize their potential.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

When selecting productive tasks, you must follow the following requirements:

1. As a result of completing the task, the student must receive a new final product.
2. Tasks should have a social and cultural significance.
3. The task should update the knowledge, skills, and personal experience of students.

Reproductive tasks should be performed according to a given pattern [7]. When determining the individual trajectories of students, it is necessary to remember that as a result of training, each student must reach the minimum threshold set by the discipline program. The teacher is forced to "balance" between the requirements of the Program and the actual level of the student, so some "easing" for poorly prepared students should be compensated by the intensity of their study of the material. For example, for such students, it is possible to enlarge the units of the training content, setting the task of mastering a large amount of material "from scratch", but at the reproductive level. The implementation of personality-oriented learning in the conditions of differentiation of the learning process can be carried out through the use of technologies of collective and group learning. The specifics of collective learning, as is known, consist in the presence of different types of groups (permanent or mobile subgroups, replaceable or permanent pairs). In these groups, there is mutual learning, mutual control and mutual management of students in the classroom (with the leading role of the teacher!). When using this technology, it is necessary to establish the requirements for mastering the theoretical and practical material for each subgroup. The requirements are the volume of the material being studied, as well as the skills and abilities that a student of a particular subgroup should master. The criterion for the formation of groups or pairs can be the level of proficiency in the educational material (i.e., the level of knowledge). well-and poorly prepared students make up different groups with the goals of mastering different materials), and it is possible to consciously and purposefully form heterogeneous groups by " introducing "one or more" strong "

students into each group of poorly prepared students with the assignment of guiding and controlling functions to them. In the latter case, more prepared students play the role of "consultants", "bosses". This "staging" is a powerful means of achieving teaching, developing and educating goals, because when a person teaches others, he most deeply understands and remembers the material [8, p. 247]. The role of "bosses" can be transferred to different students after they reach a certain level, which is also an incentive to master the subject. "The group form of educational work in a foreign language lesson gives a lot: it develops the ability to learn, provides better conditions for the ability to speak, provides knowledge exchange, promotes the growth of motivation to learn, strengthens interpersonal relationships, teaches us to better understand each other" [9, p.245]. An important factor in the need to use group forms of work in the classroom is a positive attitude towards them on the part of the students themselves, which is reflected in the positive dynamics of the development of the material. "Students see the most attractive side of the group form of education in the possibility of joint activities and communication in the classroom. This allows you to establish business and personal contacts, to ensure a certain group status. However, a desirable partner in joint activities can only be made with a responsible attitude to teaching. Thus, the desire to realize the motives of communication puts them in front of the need to engage in educational work. This, in turn, leads to the formation of educational motives, which in the future can take a dominant position in the motivational sphere of the individual " [10]. It should also be noted that the methods of collective learning, such as the interchange of tasks, performing exercises in pairs (groups), mutual dictation allow you to unite a group that is heterogeneous in terms of language proficiency, provide each student with conditions for self-realization and self-development, and save study time. Properly organized training involves not only accounting, but also the development of individual learning abilities of students through the use of creative methods of educational work. Such techniques allow you to go ahead of the existing level of students and purposefully form the skills of creative speech-thinking activity. Here we "come to the aid" of game technologies (debates, business games), technologies of active and problem-based learning (seminars, discussions, classes in the form of "brainstorming"), as well as the project method. The latter is based on active activitybased learning, taking into account the student's personal interest in gaining knowledge. The project method " is a development of the concept of learning in collaboration and is based on modeling social interaction in the study group during classes or during extracurricular hours. Students distribute their responsibilities for the implementation of the project and in the process of solving real problem problems form the skills of interaction, learn to work in a team" [11, p. 24]. The main goal of the teacher in this case is to show students their personal interest in the acquired knowledge that can be useful to them in life. To do this, a problem that is significant for the student is taken from real life, to solve which he needs to apply the knowledge obtained during the implementation of the project. The teacher acts as a coordinator in obtaining this knowledge, can suggest the necessary sources of

information or simply direct the students' thoughts in the right direction for independent search. As a result, students must independently and jointly solve the problem by applying the acquired knowledge. Differentiation of learning outcomes allows the teacher to change the requirements for completing tasks for students of different levels: lower for students of a relatively low level and increase for students of an advanced level. When working in a group, it is necessary to evaluate each student separately. If you give an overall grade, some students will get too high scores, while others will be underestimated.

CONCLUSION

To conclude, the use of differentiated teaching methods allows us to equalize the contradiction between the diversity of the language student group and the need to form the necessary level of foreign language communicative competence for all students. This is done by taking into account the individual characteristics of each student and building training according to individual educational trajectories. Thus, personality-oriented differentiated learning corresponds to the paradigm of modern education, which puts the student's personality in the center of attention. The result of the introduction of personality-oriented differentiated learning is a truly effective language education.

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